

Functional Remission and Diagnostic Shift in Autism Spectrum Disorder: Effectiveness of a Naturopathic Intervention in a Single Case

Katia Dolle

Aitor Garcia Galardi

2025

Abstract

Introduction: Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental condition characterized by marked etiological and clinical heterogeneity. In recent years, there has been growing recognition of the need to investigate integrative approaches that consider its potential multisystem nature. From the perspective of complex systems theory, effective interventions should necessarily be multidimensional and adaptive.

Case presentation: A 4-year-old girl was evaluated for socio-communicative regression and sensory alterations. A diagnosis of moderate-to-severe ASD was confirmed using standardized assessments (ADOS-2, ADI-R, Battelle), which demonstrated a developmental profile significantly below her chronological age.

Intervention: An individualized complex naturopathic intervention was implemented over 24 months, comprising three core components: 1) trophology (correction of dysbiosis and hypersensitivity); 2) naturopathic supplementation (a sequential and rotational regimen with periodic laboratory assessment); and 3) parental coaching (behavioral management and neurodevelopmental stimulation).

Results: An 85.7% reduction in symptom severity was observed (ATEC: 112 → 16), along with a 30-point increase in the general development index (DP-3), equivalent to approximately 2

standard deviations. Clinical evolution showed the progressive acquisition of functional language, social skills, and behavioral regulation. Final external reassessments revealed a relevant diagnostic discrepancy: a non-blinded evaluation maintained the ASD diagnosis (based on ADOS-2), whereas an independent blinded hospital-based assessment ruled out ASD, identifying only a severe expressive language disorder.

Conclusions: The intervention was associated with an accelerated clinical trajectory toward functional remission (*optimal outcome*), with persistence of neurodivergent traits centered on language. The case illustrates a phenomenon of *diagnostic overshadowing* in the presence of severe phonological deficits, particularly when observational tools such as the ADOS-2 are used. These findings support the potential functional impact of early multimodal naturopathic approaches and underscore the need for independent diagnostic reassessment at more advanced developmental levels.

Keywords: autism spectrum disorder, functional remission, diagnostic overshadowing, naturopathic intervention, single-case study

Introduction

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental condition with heterogeneous etiology. [1–3] International guidelines recognize the need to investigate multimodal interventions that address its potential multisystem involvement. [4–6] In this context, an individualized complex naturopathic intervention (hereafter, CNI) was implemented, protocolized under the designation Katia Dolle Method® (hereafter, KDM). This CNI targets interrelated biological imbalances associated with behavioral disturbances through strategies including immunonutrition, supplementation, and structured parental support, aimed at modulating immunological, neuroendocrine, and behavioral axes. This report documents the longitudinal evolution of a single case involving a 4-year-old girl who received this CNI,

evaluating the impact of modulating underlying biological factors on the severity of her initial diagnosis.

Case Presentation

Following a typical developmental trajectory, this Mexican girl experienced socio-communicative regression at 18 months of age. At 48 months (December 2022), independent external professionals diagnosed moderate-to-severe ASD, documenting a markedly impaired baseline across multiple neurodevelopmental domains (Table 1). Three months later, due to lack of response to conventional approaches, the family discontinued previous therapies and initiated the CNI as the sole intervention. Key anamnestic data and initial laboratory findings—documenting intestinal dysbiosis, non-IgE-mediated food hypersensitivity, elevated metals, and reduced mineral levels—are summarized in Table 2.

Table 1

Initial Diagnostic Assessment

Assessment	Result	Interpretation
ADOS-2	7 out of 10 points	Moderate-to-severe autism
ADI-R	Abnormalities in the development of social interaction and communication	Consistent with ASD diagnosis
Batelle	Developmental age: 23 months (chronological age: 48 months)	Global developmental delay
GARS	78% probability of behaviors associated with autism	High probability of ASD
Sensory Profile-2	Sensory-seeking pattern	Increased need for auditory, tactile, and vestibular stimuli
Language assessment	Preverbal skills equivalent to 4 months (chronological age: 48 months)	Impairments across all language domains (semantic, morphosyntactic, phonological, and pragmatic)
Qualitative clinical observations	Greater interest in objects than in people; poor eye contact; no spontaneous response to name; lack of reciprocity across different activities; absence of verbal output; difficulty producing and understanding communicative gestures; vocal stereotypies; no evidence spontaneous symbolic play; limited shared enjoyment; absence of	

Assessment	Result	Interpretation
	reciprocal social smiling; reduced facial expressiveness; lack of appropriate social initiations; disruptive behaviors during transitions; hand flapping; atypical sensory-seeking behaviors	
Overall clinical impression	Persistent deficits in social reciprocity, communicative intent, verbal communication, and spontaneous use of gestures to convey goal-directed cognitive states; impairments in social initiation and response, and joint attention; difficulties in the use of descriptive, conventional, instrumental, and/or emotional gestures; absence of spontaneous symbolic play; limited peer interaction; presence of stereotyped movements and atypical sensory behaviors	

Note. ADOS-2: Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule, Second Edition; ADI-R: Autism Diagnostic Interview–Revised; Battelle: Battelle Developmental Inventory; GARS: Gilliam Autism Rating Scale; Sensory Profile-2: Dunn’s Sensory Profile, Second Edition.

Table 2

Baseline Clinical and Biological Findings

Category	Findings
Parent-reported behavioral characteristics	Hypersensitivity to physical contact and loud sounds; high emotional reactivity; disruptive behaviors (tantrums, aggression, occasional self-injury); absence of expressive language; limited comprehension; social withdrawal; absence of functional play; reduced pain response; low risk awareness; tendency to wander; tactile defensiveness; severe food selectivity
Urinary analysis	Elevated metals: As, Cd, Cs, Pb, Hg, Cu Reduced minerals: Ca, Se, Fe, Mg, P, Cr, B, Zn
Fecal microbiology	Intestinal dysbiosis with altered commensal flora and presence of potentially pathogenic genera (<i>Citrobacter</i> , <i>Enterobacter</i> , <i>Klebsiella</i>), as well as yeasts
Blood biochemistry	ALT: 52 U/L; creatinine: 0.46 mg/dL; dopamine: 116 pg/mL; cortisol: 13.3 µg/dL
Food hypersensitivity (Gell and Coombs type III reaction)	Elevated reactions to oats, barley, spelt, gluten, wheat, rye, lemon, lettuce, egg, and almond

Note. As: arsenic; Cd: cadmium; Cs: cesium; Pb: lead; Hg: mercury; Cu: copper; Ca: calcium; Se: selenium; Fe: iron; Mg: magnesium; P: phosphorus; Cr: chromium; B: boron; Zn: zinc; ALT: alanine aminotransferase.

Intervention

A multimodal and individualized CNI (KDM) was implemented over 24 months of active intervention. The follow-up period (March 2023 – September 2025) included intermittent logistical delays totaling 7 months due to customs-related issues in supplement importation. The reported functional changes correspond to 24 net months of effective ICN, which was structured into three core components:

(1) trophology: the elimination and substitution of foods that trigger delayed hypersensitivity reactions, aimed at reducing inflammatory cytokine cascades and correcting dysbiosis.

(2) naturopathic supplementation: a sequential and rotational regimen, organized into bimonthly blocks and reassessed every six months through laboratory testing, aimed at immunological, neurological, and neuroendocrine modulation, as well as detoxification processes.

(3) parental coaching: training in health-related care, behavioral management, and structured neurocognitive stimulation in the home setting (language, motor skills, and social abilities).

Continuous therapeutic monitoring was conducted remotely, with no adverse effects throughout the intervention.

Follow-up and Outcomes

Periodic laboratory assessments, psychometric evaluations, and parent-reported data collected throughout the intervention documented a progressive clinical–biological evolution (Tables 3 and 4, Figure 1).

Table 3

Longitudinal Evolution of Psychometric and Biological Parameters

Date	Assessment	Results
March 2023	ATEC	Total score: 112 (severe range)
March 2023	Laboratory analyses (urine, fecal microbiology, blood biochemistry, and food reactivity)	Elevated metals, essential mineral deficiencies, intestinal dysbiosis, alterations in blood biochemical parameters, and positive food reactivity (see Table 2)
March 2023	EEG	Abnormal graphoelements; immature rhythm
April 2023	ATEC	Total score: 77 (moderate-to-severe range)
November 2023	DP-3	General Development Index: 62 (very low range)
November 2023	ATEC	Total score: 38 (mild-to-moderate range)
November 2023	Raven	Standard score: 122 (high range)
November 2023	SENA	Developmental delay: 77; Rigidity: 70; Emotional regulation problems: 61; Personal resources: 21; Social integration: 26; Emotional intelligence: 22
May 2024	EEG	Fronto-temporal irritative activity
May 2024	DP-3	General Development Index: 83 (low range)
May 2024	Fecal microbiology analysis	Reduction of pathogenic bacteria; yeasts negative
October 2024	Laboratory analyses (urine and blood biochemistry)	Elevated metals: Cd, Cs, Pb, Ni ALT: 100 U/L; AST: 37 U/L; EBV nuclear antigen IgG: 421.0 U/mL; dopamine <45 pg/mL; cortisol: 11.6 µg/dL
November 2024	ATEC	Total score: 16 (mild range)
November 2024	DP-3	General Development Index: 91 (average range)
November 2024	SENA	Developmental delay: 67; Rigidity: 41; Emotional regulation problems: 37; Personal resources: 48; Social integration: 54; Emotional intelligence: 43
September 2025	SENA	Developmental delay: 72; Rigidity: 44; Emotional regulation problems: 40; Personal resources: 52; Social integration: 46; Emotional intelligence: 57

October 2025	DP-3	General Development Index: 93 (average range)
--------------	------	---

Note. ATEC: Autism Treatment Evaluation Checklist; DP-3: Developmental Profile-3; SENA: Child and Adolescent Assessment System; EEG: electroencephalogram; ALT: alanine aminotransferase; AST: aspartate aminotransferase.

Table 4

Longitudinal Evolution of Qualitative Clinical Milestones Reported by Caregivers

Date	Parent-reported observations
March 2023	Severe ASD symptomatology: absence of verbal language, sensory dysfunction, disruptive behaviors, and limited social responsiveness
April 2023	Emergence of basic functional interaction; improved comprehension and imitation
May 2023	Sensory and behavioral improvement; increased tolerance to stimuli and ability to follow instructions
June 2023	Full bladder and bowel control achieved
July 2023	Resolution of food selectivity and increased basic autonomy
August 2023	Improved social responsiveness and emergence of affective behaviors
September 2023	Increased social interaction and vocal imitation
October 2023	Improved attention, fine motor skills, and interest in symbolic activities
November 2023	Reduced rigidity and improved environmental adaptation
December 2023	Onset of verbal language with communicative intent
January 2024	Letter recognition and initial global reading
February 2024	Vocabulary expansion and functional use of language
March 2024	Begins to request desired items; disappearance of screen-related preoccupation
April 2024	Increased sensory and behavioral flexibility
May 2024	Improved social understanding and socio-emotional language
June 2024	Use of five-word sentences and improved conversational comprehension
July 2024	Improved emotional regulation in stressful situations
August 2024	Cognitive and social development consistent with age
September 2024	Onset of reading and writing; spontaneous use of verbs and concepts
October 2024	Emergence of complex symbolic play
November 2024	High adaptive functioning in daily contexts, with persistent difficulties in structured language
January 2025	Greater communicative precision (expression of refusal and preferences) and improved fine motor skills

Date	Parent-reported observations
February 2025	Consolidation of instruction comprehension and emergence of basic abstract concepts
March 2025	Increased structural complexity of language and social imitation
April 2025	Use of language in more specific contexts and improved guided reading comprehension
May 2025	Emergence of verbal empathy and improved behavioral self-regulation
June 2025	Development of functional abstract thinking and consolidation of symbolic play
July 2025	Prosocial behaviors and complete sensory adaptation
August 2025	Consolidation of functional language and temporal understanding
September 2025	Generalization of spontaneous communication across different contexts

Note. Clinical milestones were reported by caregivers during therapeutic follow-up based on non-standardized observational records and reflect perceived functional changes in the child’s daily environment.

Neuropsychological Metrics

Psychometric assessment showed longitudinal changes across the evaluated domains (Figure 1, Table 4). Autism severity decreased from 112 points (severe range) to 16 (mild range), as measured by the ATEC.

In general development (DP-3), scores improved from very low (63) to the low range (83) at six months, reaching the average range (91) by the end of the intervention. At long-term follow-up (October 2025), a score of 93 was recorded. This 30-point increase is approximately equivalent to 2 standard deviations (SD).

In the socioemotional profile (SENA), problematic indicators decreased (e.g., rigidity from 70 to 41), along with an increase in adaptive capacities (e.g., social integration from 26 to 54). At the final assessment (September 2025), some dimensions showed slight variations, whereas others, such as emotional intelligence, continued to improve (from 22 to 57).

Overall, the data indicate a significant longitudinal improvement in symptomatology and functioning across behavioral, cognitive, and socioemotional domains.

Figure 1. Longitudinal evolution of ATEC, DP-3, and SENA scores throughout follow-up

Note. (A) Longitudinal evolution of autism symptom severity assessed using the Autism Treatment Evaluation Checklist (ATEC), showing a progressive reduction from values consistent with severe impairment to levels below 30, compatible with low symptom severity. (B) Developmental progression assessed using the Developmental Profile-3 (DP-3), with a gradual increase reaching the average range (dashed line at index = 85). (C) Changes in the socio-emotional profile assessed using the Child and Adolescent Assessment System (SENA) at three time points, showing a downward trend in problematic dimensions and an upward trend in adaptive capacities.

External Neuropsychological Reassessments

Following completion of the intervention, when the child was 6 years and 11 months old (October 2025), two external assessments were conducted (Table 5). Assessment A (conducted

with prior knowledge of the case) reported a developmental age of 68 months (Battelle Developmental Inventory) and a nonverbal IQ of 121 (TONI-2), and resulted an ASD level 1 diagnosis based on ADOS-2 scores.

In contrast, Assessment B (an independent hospital-based evaluation, blinded to the previous diagnosis) reported a perceptual IQ of 94 and a verbal IQ of 53 using the WISC-IV. Scores on the BANFE-2 battery and the ICADIP scale (70% in social skills) fell within normative ranges. This evaluation concluded that ASD diagnostic criteria were not met, identifying only a severe expressive language deficit.

Table 5

Comparison of External Neuropsychological Reassessments

Assessment	Methodology	Instruments and Tests	Key Results and Scores	Diagnostic Conclusion
Assessment A, cognitive rehabilitation center (October 2025)	With prior knowledge of the initial diagnosis (non-blinded)	Battelle, TONI-2, ADOS-2, GARS, ELO, CUMANIN, Melgar Test	Developmental age: 68 months; nonverbal IQ: 121; ADOS-2 score: 18	Autism spectrum disorder (ASD), level 1
Assessment B, specialized hospital center (October 2025)	Without prior knowledge of the diagnosis (blinded)	WISC-IV, BANFE-2, ICADIP, ENI-2, DTVP-3, Sensory Profile-2	Perceptual IQ: 94; verbal IQ: 53; normal orbitomedial cortical functioning; social skills (ICADIP): 70%	ASD not confirmed; severe expressive language deficit

Note. ADOS-2: Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule, Second Edition; ADI-R: Autism Diagnostic Interview–Revised; Battelle: Battelle Developmental Inventory; GARS: Gilliam Autism Rating Scale; TONI-2: Test of Nonverbal Intelligence, Second Edition; WISC-IV: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, Fourth Edition; BANFE-2: Neuropsychological Battery of Executive Functions; ICADIP: Adaptive Behavior Inventory; ENI-2: Child Neuropsychological Assessment; DTVP-3: Developmental Test of Visual Perception, Third Edition; Sensory Profile-2: Dunn’s Sensory Profile, Second Edition.

Discussion

The results suggest that the CNI contributed to an evolution consistent with functional remission, or *optimal outcome*, as described in the literature. [7] After 24 months of active intervention, the main residual finding was a severe expressive language deficit. The marked divergence between external reassessments illustrates a clear case of *diagnostic overshadowing* in the presence of language comorbidities. [8] Assessment B demonstrated an intact neurobiological substrate for empathy (functional orbitomedial cortex), suggesting that motor-phonological impairment (verbal IQ: 53) was misinterpreted by the ADOS-2 (in Assessment A) as a lack of communicative intent, leading to a structural false positive, as described in the literature. [9,10]

In this context, the CNI was oriented toward the modulation of altered biological systems, including intestinal dysbiosis, food hypersensitivity, micronutrient imbalances, and heavy metal burden, through strategies such as immunonutrition, supplementation, and parental training, in line with studies linking gastrointestinal dysfunction and micronutrient deficiencies to ASD. [11–13] The observed efficacy may reflect the integrated modulation of these interdependent systems, consistent with the framework of complex systems theory. Although single-case reports do not allow for robust causal inferences, the discontinuation of other therapies, the convergence of psychometric improvements, and validation through independent, blinded external neuropsychological assessments may suggest a clinically relevant effect of the intervention.

Conclusions

Through a 24-month active ICN intervention, a 4-year-old girl achieved an 85.7% reduction in autism severity (ATEC) and an approximately 2 SD increase in the developmental index (DP-3), substantially narrowing the functional gap with her peers. These results suggest functional remission (*optimal outcome*), accompanied by residual neurodivergence dominated by a developmental language disorder. This finding highlights potential structural limitations of observational tools such as the ADOS-2 at more advanced developmental levels, particularly in

the presence of severe phonological deficits, consistent with a phenomenon of diagnostic overshadowing. Finally, this case study provides preliminary evidence supporting the functional impact of early multimodal naturopathic interventions on neurodevelopment.

Patient Perspective

The parents expressed appreciation not only for addressing their daughter's biological challenges, but also for being taught how to sustain improvements over time:

“Being shown a step-by-step path and realizing how much depends on the work (stimulation) I provide to my daughter now that the biological aspects are being addressed is truly remarkable. Before, I had the desire to help her, but I didn't know how, what to prioritize, or what should come first. The biological issues prevented any real connection—she did not recognize me—which made daily life extremely difficult and frustrating.”

Informed Consent

The authors certify that they have obtained all appropriate consent forms from the parents of the child. In these forms, the parents provided consent for the publication of images and other information related to the case.

The parents understand that their names and initials will not be published and that every effort will be made to conceal their identity, although anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding

This study received no external funding. The costs associated with the intervention, follow-up,

and analysis were fully covered by the Katia Dolle Foundation, with no financial burden on the participating family.

References

- [1] Conchari Cabrera ML. (2024). Factores epigenéticos en los trastornos del espectro autista: un enfoque integral. *Revista de Investigación e Información en Salud*, 19(47), 86–93.
- [2] Pardo-Govea T, Solís-Áñez E. (2009). Aspectos inmunogenéticos del autismo: revisión. *Investigación Clínica*, 50(3), 393–406.
- [3] Arberas C, Ruggieri V. (2013). Autismo y epigenética: un modelo de explicación para la comprensión de la génesis en los trastornos del espectro autista. *Medicina (Buenos Aires)*, 73(Suppl. I), 20–29.
- [4] Ozler E, Sanlier N. (2025). Nutritional approaches in autism spectrum disorder: a scoping review. *Current Nutrition Reports*, 14(1), 61.
- [5] Daniel KS, Jiang Q, Wood MS. (2025). The increasing prevalence of autism spectrum disorder in the U.S. and its implications for pediatric micronutrient status: a narrative review of case reports and series. *Nutrients*, 17(6), 990.
- [6] Al-Beltagi M. (2024). Nutritional management and autism spectrum disorder: a systematic review. *World Journal of Clinical Pediatrics*, 13(4), 99649.
- [7] Fein D, Barton M, Eigsti IM, et al. (2013). Optimal outcome in individuals with a history of autism. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 54(2), 195–205.
- [8] Gupta M, et al. (2025). The challenges of autism spectrum disorder diagnosis: comorbidities and diagnostic overshadowing. Cambridge University Press.

- [9] Leyfer OT, Tager-Flusberg H, Dowd M, et al. (2008). Overlap between autism and specific language impairment: comparison of Autism Diagnostic Interview and Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule scores. *Autism Research*, 1(5), 284–296.
- [10] Greene RK, Vasile I, Bradbury KR, et al. (2022). Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule (ADOS-2) elevations in a clinical sample of children and adolescents who do not have autism: phenotypic profiles of false positives. *The Clinical Neuropsychologist*, 36(5), 943–959.
- [11] Coury DL, Ashwood P, Fasano A, et al. (2012). Gastrointestinal conditions in children with autism spectrum disorder: developing a research agenda. *Pediatrics*, 130(Suppl 2), S160–S168.
- [12] Adams JB, Audhya T, Geis E, et al. (2018). Comprehensive nutritional and dietary intervention for autism spectrum disorder: a randomized, controlled 12-month trial. *Nutrients*, 10(3), 369.
- [13] Deb SS, Retzer A, Roy M, et al. (2020). The effectiveness of parent training for children with autism spectrum disorder: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Psychiatry*, 20(1), 583.